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What network and performance indicators can tell us about supply chain and sourcing resilience (and what they cannot)

Dmitry Ivanov

Berlin School of Economics and Law, Department of Business Administration, Professor for Supply Chain and Operations Management, 10825, Berlin, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Supply chain (SC) resilience takes network connectivity and performance persistence perspectives, which supplement each other. The extant literature has developed a large body of knowledge about SC resilience's network and performance indicators. However, we are unaware of any published research combining these two perspectives in resilience assessment. Therefore, this study aims to advance our understanding of how network and performance indicators can mutually enhance each other when analysing SC resilience as both a system property (quality) and an outcome (quantity). The unique contribution of our study is a combined use of network science and discrete-event simulation allowing for mixed-method grounded integration of static and dynamic views of supply chain resilience. Using node degrees as network indicators and on-time delivery, fulfilment rate, and time-to-recovery as performance indicators, we examine reactions of these indicators to a disruption to the sourcing strategies of three different flexibility degrees. We observe that network science methods can be used to identify disruption existence while simulation methods allow quantifying performance impact. We show how and when the combined application of network and performance indicators can inform decision-makers about SC resilience, and propose a generalised guideline for a practical implementation of the developed approach. Our main conclusion is that SC resilience-assessment models can be mutually enhanced by including network characteristics and process dynamics through a combination of network analysis and simulation.

1. Introduction

The supply chain (SC) literature has increasingly highlighted the importance of resilience (Garvey et al., 2015; DuHadway et al., 2019, Burkhart and Bode, 2024). In SC resilience, assessment and measurement problems play a vital role (Hägele et al., 2023; Hosseini et al., 2019; Brusset et al., 2023; Schoenherr et al., 2023). In generalised terms, there are two major approaches to measuring the resilience of SCs. The first approach takes the network perspective. Its focus is on quantifying the ability of a network to maintain its structural connectivity and adaptability (Chauhan et al., 2021; Namdar et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2023). Here, the resilience is seen as a network quality. The second approach considers SC performance deviations (e.g., on-time delivery) as indicators of disruptions. Thus, resilience is viewed as both a quantity and an outcome (Ivanov and Dolgui, 2021; Jackson et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024).

From the SC performance perspective, the main assumption is that a disruption hits the SC, and its effect is seen in some performance deviation. A network-based view of SC resilience offers a theory of actions

(adaptation) to ensure that things go right (a focus on performance persistence through network connectivity and adaptability). A performance-based view focuses on failures to avoid things going wrong (a focus on failure) (Ivanov 2024).

Both views are important and contribute to resilience understanding in SCs, suggesting the academic and practical relevance of novel approaches to quantifying resilience based on measuring network properties and performance. It is important to measure losses from disruptions and quantify the success, as materialised in performance, obtained by preventing disruptions through resilience practices in the SC (Ivanov, 2023b).

The extant literature offers many works on both network and performance indicators (Ivanov and Sokolov, 2013; Lückner et al., 2021; Rozhkov et al., 2022). However, we are unaware of any published research combining network and performance indicators in resilience assessment. The objective of this study is, therefore, to advance our understanding of how network and performance indicators can mutually enhance each other when analysing SC resilience as both a system property (quality) and an outcome (quantity).

E-mail address: divanov@hwr-berlin.de.

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Four research questions motivate our work:

1. How can network and performance indicators mutually enhance each other to measure SC resilience as both a property and an outcome?
2. When and how can network and performance indicators inform about disruptions and recovery considering time delays?
3. What managerial insights can be obtained from a combined analysis of network and performance indicators?

Our paper uses graph-theoretical methods to analyse SC resilience (Sokolov et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020) and discrete-event simulation using anyLogistix software (Ivanov, 2020; Singh et al., 2021). Our main analysis logic is as follows. We first describe the computation of different indicators. We then illustrate them using three network examples with low, partial, and full connectivity and adaptability. After running a simulation model to capture the disruption dynamics, we derive managerial insights on the individual and combined use of network and performance indicators.

We contribute to the literature as follows. The unique contribution of our study is a combined use of network science and discrete-event simulation allowing for mixed-method grounded integration of static and dynamic views of supply chain resilience. We show how the network and simulation methods can enrich each other in resilience analysis. Our experiments distinctively illustrate shortcomings of static methods based on dynamic analysis. We deduce important managerial recommendations on when and how different resilience indicators can be used by managers when analysing SC resilience. Our paper is the first in the SC and operations-management literature to measure and analyse SC resilience from both a network and performance perspective. It provides several insights relevant to SC managers and academics. First, we analyse the benefits of both network and performance indicators. We show that it is beneficial to use network indicators, such as in-degree and out-degree, for the analysis of structural connectivity and disruption identification. The same holds true for fulfilment rate (FR) as a performance indicator. On the other hand, on-time delivery (OTD) and time-to-recover (TTR) help quantify the effect of a disruption to measure resilience as outcome or quantity. However, they are less helpful to the operative recognition of disruptions. Second, we examine the indicators within each group (network and performance). Our findings reveal that delivery reliability provides a more realistic understanding of inventory and warehouse-operations disruptions, while on-time delivery shows the ripple-effect exposure of an SC (disruption propagation to the customer) and performance effect of a disruption. In the group of network indicators, in-degree and out-degree allow disruptions to be detected through changes in structural connectivity. Third, we propose a simulation example to illustrate the application of network and performance indicators. We demonstrate that SC resilience models can be mutually enhanced through the inclusion of adaptability and connectivity characteristics of the network elements with consideration of time and flow dynamics. This can be achieved through a combination of network analysis and simulation. Together, our findings show that SC resilience can be measured both as a quality and a quantity based on a combination of network and performance indicators.

The remainder of our study is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a literature review. In section 3, the computation major indicators used in this study is explained. Section 4 illustrates the analysis through a numerical example. Section 5 reports sensitivity analysis results. The managerial insights and practical implementation are discussed in Section 6, and the main findings are summarised in Section 7.

2. Literature review

Measuring the effect of disruptions on SC performance has usually focused on deviations in OTD, service level, and perfect order (Ivanov, 2021b; Sawik, 2022; Rozhkov, 2022). For example, Singh et al. (2021)

and Ivanov (2020) measured decreases in OTD due to disruption as a ratio of on-time delivered orders to the total number of orders placed. Resilience was quantified by 1 minus the fraction of loss, so the metric was bounded between 0 and 1. This approach follows methods of measuring SC resilience as the intensity of performance loss and recovery (Torabi et al., 2015; Zobel et al., 2021; Ivanov 2025a). With the focus on recovery time and consideration of some reserves in the SC that can help cope with material shortages, Simchi-Levi et al. (2015) proposed measuring SC resilience using supplier risk exposure. They compared TTR and time-to-survive, and an SC was considered resilient if TTR was less than time-to-survive. Important research relevant to our study is the ripple effect, i.e., disruption propagation (Ghadge et al., 2013; Ivanov and Dolgui, 2021; Garvey and Carnovale, 2020).

Kinra et al. (2020) extended this approach toward ripple effect assessment: i.e., disruption propagation. Their model is based on an SC's possible maximum loss if a disruption propagates through the network, resulting in the loss of sales. Burkhart and Bode (2024) used disruption intensity (disruption frequency \times disruption duration) to investigate the relationship between supplier performance and supply chain disruptions.

While observations of performance deviations through relevant indicators are important, one common shortcoming of these methods is their lack of insight into the influencing factors and parameters that affect performance variations. Some research has addressed this problem considering both performance deviations and factors that lead to changes in some performance indicators. Torabi et al. (2015) and Zobel et al. (2021) measured SC resilience based on shortages and recovery time. Hosseini and Ivanov (2022) and Liu et al. (2021) used Bayesian networks to quantify resilience. They considered both risk events and their consequences in terms of performance deviations.

Network theory studies proposed a variety of means to measure SC resilience. For example, degree and betweenness centrality, connectivity, and reachability coefficients have been used to quantify structural integrity, connectivity, and flexibility (Wagner and Neshat, 2010; Sokolov et al., 2016; Tan et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021). One essential problem in using network metrics is the focus on structure rather than effect along with missing considerations of material flow dynamics (Ivanov 2025b).

In summary, the literature recognises structural stability and process continuity as main indicators of SC resilience. Despite the indisputable value of measuring network characteristics and performance indicators individually, understanding their relationship is also important. The analysis of the extant literature allows us to conclude that network characteristics can help obtain a static assessment of structural variety and flexibility and partially consider flows. These methods, however, are static and do not cover real dynamics (e.g., ordering policies, lead-time delays, and inventory dynamics). In addition, a graph usually describes only the organisational network, while the product level (i.e., the bill of materials [BOM]) remains relatively untouched. SC resilience analysis implies both adaptability and connectivity characteristics in the network and consideration of time and flow dynamics. In this setting, simulation in combination with network theory is interesting for analysis of both structural and flow layers.

3. Indicators

In this section, we explain the main network and performance indicators used in our study and their computation and managerial meaning. These indicators have been considered in the previous studies individually, either in the network analysis area (Li et al., 2020) or simulation (Singh et al., 2021). Correspondingly, the insights known to data are limited to particular settings (i.e., network level without consideration of process dynamics and process dynamics simulation without considering network level) (Mosayebi et al., 2024). Our unique contribution is a combination of these two views allowing for extending the existing insights at the network level through consideration of the

dynamic process simulation, and *vice versa*.

We begin with the network indicators. For this study, two indicators were selected in line with the extant literature (e.g., Li et al., 2020; Ivanov, 2021, chapter 4): in- and out-degrees of nodes. The in-degree of a node X, $\text{deg}_{\text{in}}(X)$, is the number of edges that end at the vertex X. The out-degree of a node X, $\text{deg}_{\text{out}}(X)$, is the number of edges that originate at the vertex X and point outward to other vertices.

Note 1: we restrict ourselves to node degree indicators without including other typical graph-theoretical measures of centrality, connectivity, or reachability (Sokolov et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020). Without loss of generality, we use node degrees to illustrate the role and information the network indicators can provide to a decision-maker, contrasting them with performance indicators. This is in line with the main objective of this study, which is to describe two views of SC resilience assessment throughout the network and performance perspectives rather than to engage in a complex graph-theoretical analysis when the complexity will not necessarily lead to additional insights that can be shown in a simple but illustrative example.

We now turn to performance indicators. In line with the literature (Simchi-Levi et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2021), OTD, FR, and TTR are included in our analysis. OTD is the ratio of customer orders delivered on time to all orders placed by the customers (Eq. (1)).

$$\text{OTD} = \frac{\text{number of on-time orders}}{\text{total number of orders placed}} \quad (1)$$

FR is the ratio of orders successfully fulfilled from available inventory-on-hand to the total number of orders placed (Eq. (2)).

$$\text{FR} = \frac{\text{number of customer orders successfully fulfilled from available inventory-on-hand}}{\text{total number of orders placed}} \quad (2)$$

We also introduce an indicator that is similar to FR but with a slightly different focus: fulfilment structure rate (FSR; Eq. (3)).

$$\text{FSR} = \frac{\text{number of warehouses successfully fulfilling customer orders from available inventory-on-hand}}{\text{total number of warehouses}} \quad (3)$$

FSR reflects the structural component of the fulfilment process, and its values can differ from those of FR. Consider an example (see Fig. 2). In case 2a, the orders of customer nodes 7 and 8 are not fulfilled, so both FR and FSR equal 0.6 (assuming equally proportional demand across all five customers, 7–11). In case 2b, however, warehouse node 4 serves customer demand at node 4. In this case, FR will be 0.8, but FSR will remain 0.6 since both warehouses 7 and 8 are still out of operation and not fulfilling orders.

Both FR/FSR and OTD can help reflect the effect of SC disruptions and resilience. The values of the nominators of Eqs. (2) and (3) might be reduced if inventories are unavailable (Eq. (3)) or deliveries are late (Eq. (2)), caused by a disruption or the ripple effect. While OTD reflects the customer performance effect of a disruption (e.g., late delivery), FR takes the warehouse perspective, reflecting reduced responsiveness in order fulfilment due to a disruption.

TTR is the next performance indicator we use in this study. The original meaning of TTR (Simchi-Levi et al., 2015) was to measure the period during which a disrupted network element (e.g., a supplier) was able to recover (or a company was able to find a replacement for the

disrupted node: e.g., a backup supplier). In contrast to this original meaning and in line with the objectives of our study, we measure TTR based on two performance thresholds: failure and recovery service level (FR and OTD, respectively) of the SC (Eq. (4)).

$$\text{TTR} = t_{\text{service level recovery}} - t_{\text{service level failure}} \quad (4)$$

For example, if a service level value falls below the minimum admissible threshold (e.g., 95 %) during disruption simulation, it indicates a disruption, and if it returns to any value above the target service level (e.g., 98 %), it indicates the disruption's end. TTR is then computed as the point of time of target service level recovery minus the point of time when service level fell below the minimum threshold.

4. Modelling and examples

4.1. Network structures and disruptions

We use a real-life example of a multi-regional retail network and examine three network structures with different sourcing policies (single sourcing, multiple sourcing, and full flexibility) which have been used in real life for analysis of SC resilience for a fast-moving consumer good (FMCG) product (Fig. 1).

The rationale behind examining different sourcing structure echoes the recent literature underlying the crucial role of sourcing and supply resilience (Kähkönen and Patrucco, 2022). While the network structures with different sourcing policies shown in Fig. 1 have been taken from a company context (i.e., a multi-regional retail network for FMCG prod-

ucts), they can be found across different industries. For example, a single sourcing policy (Fig. 1a) has been considered by Aldrighetti et al. (2023) and is common for both retail and automotive industry. Multiple sourcing (Fig. 1b) is a common practice to hedge against disruptions in

electronics and pharmaceutical industries (Lücker et al., 2021; Sawik, 2022). Full flexibility (Fig. 1c) has been studied by Simchi-Levi et al. (2018) related to product and inventory flexibility. In summary, the three sourcing strategies considered are common across different industries. This allows for a generalization of results obtained through simulations beyond the context and data of the case-study considered.

The networks in Fig. 1 represent a SC composed of a supplier (node 1), five distribution centres (DCs, nodes 2–6), and five customer groups (nodes 7–11). DCs are located in three different regions as follows: nodes 2 and 3 belong to region I; node 4, region II; and nodes 5 and 6, region III. In the single-sourcing scenario, each DC supplies exactly one customer group. In scenario (b), there are multiple sourcing alternatives across the regions, and in scenario (c) we presume full flexibility. For disruption analysis, the unavailability of two DCs in region I (nodes 2 and 3) has been considered based on a disruption the company has experienced, which results in a decrease in network connectivity (Fig. 2).

It can be observed in Fig. 2 that the disruption at nodes 2 and 3 results in different connectivity and adaptability, depending on the

Fig. 1. Network structures with different sourcing policies.

Fig. 2. Network structures with different sourcing policies during the disruption period.

sourcing strategy. It is also intuitive that demand fulfilment will vary across these three examples. To quantify connectivity, adaptability, and demand fulfilment, we use indicators described in Section 3.

4.2. Simulation analysis

The value of simulation in the present study is to enhance the network models which are static in nature and consider only the structural view through inclusion of material flows and time-related performance analysis. Dynamic analysis of SC resilience was performed in anyLogistix software, which has been used in multiple studies for SC resilience analysis (Timperio et al., 2022). This study used the SC resilience analysis model developed in anyLogistix. We refer to (Ivanov 2017, Fig. 4 and Ivanov, 2020, Fig. 3) for a detailed model setup omitting a complex technical presentation of the model in this paper given the non-technical character of the journal. The simulation was run subject to the following main assumptions which are aligned with the real-life scenario derived through a practical project with a retail network with regards to resilience analysis for FMCG products:

- no backordering is allowed for demand (i.e., a non-served demand due to a disruption cannot be recovered in future);
- total system demand is equally distributed among all five customer groups (nodes 7–11);
- warehouses work as cross-docks;

- re-routing is possible immediately without any coordination efforts and time losses, and is unconstrained for quantity;
- lead time in the SC from supplier via warehouses to customers is 3 days and therefore shorter as the duration of the disruption period.

Note 2: To clearly show the effect of a disruption, we avoid any unnecessary randomness, such as demand or lead-time uncertainties, in the simulation model. This is in line with the approach this study takes, which is to focus on managerial insights rather than on modelling complexity. We also simplify the reality by assuming equally distributed demand and immediate re-routing possibilities to focus on essential managerial insights. In Section 5, we prove through extensive sensitivity analyses that these assumptions do not influence the generalizable character of our results confirming their robustness.

A discrete-event simulation was done for a period of 365 days in which two events were defined to model the disruption and its effect, according to the scenarios shown in Fig. 2. The first event is disruption in region I, where nodes 2 and 3 are located. The second event is the recovery of nodes 2 and 3. The time gap between these two events is 45 days. Tables 1 and 2 present the numerical outcomes of our analysis.

Table 1 shows SC performance without a disruption in region I. Each value in this table can be considered the maximum possible outcome. It can be observed in Table 2 that the values of both network and performance indicators decrease in the presence of a disruption. Node degree indicators all decrease by 40 %, showing that in-degree and out-degree can be considered reliable indicators of a disruption in the SC and its

Fig. 3. Simulation performance analysis under disruption in the single-sourcing strategy.

Fig. 4. Sensitivity analysis results for different disruption duration.

Table 1
Performance and network indicators in a disruption-free scenario.

Network design	Network indicators		Performance indicators		
	deg _{in}	deg _{out}	OTD	FR	TTR
a	10	10	100	100	0
b	18	18	100	100	0
c	30	30	100	100	0

severity, regardless of the sourcing strategy used.

Fig. 3 illustrates the simulation results concerning performance indicators.

As expected, OTD depends on the sourcing strategy's reaching the maximum of 100 % under full flexibility (Fig. 2c) and deviating from the maximum threshold in cases 2a and 2b. The lowest OTD under disruption is naturally observed in the single-sourcing strategy (case 2a). Similar behaviour is observed with FR. FSR, however, does not depend on the sourcing strategy and can be considered a reliable indicator of a disruption in the network, unlike OTD and FR, which indicate the ability

Table 2
Performance and network indicators in a disruption scenario.

	Network indicators				Performance indicators						
	deg _{in}	deg _{in} ^(o)	deg _{out}	deg _{out} ^(o)	OTD	OTD ^(o)	FR	FR ^(o)	FSR	TTR (OTD _d)	TTR (FR _d)
a	6	0.40	6	0.40	0.95	0.05	0.95	0.05	0.60	45	45
b	11	0.39	11	0.39	0.98	0.02	0.98	0.02	0.60	45	45
c	18	0.40	18	0.40	1.00	0	1.00	0	0.60	0	0

to resist and absorb disruptions. Finally, TTR is equally indicated by both FR and OTD (i.e., no disruption indication in the case of full flexibility; Fig. 2c), while FSR indicates a disruption regardless of the sourcing strategy and the use of its flexibility for the recovery.

In the dynamic simulation analysis (Fig. 3), it can be observed that OTD and FR react to disruption differently with different timing. Fig. 3 provides more details. In this simulation, a new order is placed on 1 April (day #91 in the simulation period), and the disruption begins on 1 April. The FR declines on 1 April, but OTD starts decreasing on 3 April only when the order from 1 April does not arrive. This can be explained by the fact that customer orders placed on April 1 cannot be served because of DC disruptions, and so the FR reacts immediately. However, on April 1 and 2 scheduled deliveries arrive at the customers subject to the orders placed at the end of March and processed at the DC by April 1, and only on April 3rd no new deliveries arrive which translates in the OTD decrease.

The observations considered lead us to a generalizable insight. OTD indicates a disruption later than FR does, and the delay depends on the lead time and inventory-in-transit. In addition, OTD can indicate the presence of a disruption when it has in fact already ended. In our example, the disruption is over on 16 May. Consider the order placed on 16 May: it will arrive on 18 May, so only on 18 May will OTD indicate the end of the disruption, while FR will tell us on 16 May about the recovery, similarly to in- and out-degrees. The diagram “on-time products delivered at customers” shows two lines, i.e., products delivered at the nodes 7 and 8 in the planned and actual modes. This diagram nicely illustrates the deliveries in case of a non-disruption scenario (the upper line) and actual deliveries subject to the disruption on April 1 (the lower line).

5. Sensitivity analysis

In this section, we report results of extensive sensitivity analyses with 18 different settings as described in sects 5.1 and 5.2. Essentially, we build the experimental design of sensitivity analysis by relaxing some assumptions and allowing some variation in input parameters which are the most common ways of verification in simulation studies (Ross, 2022). Most importantly, we organise our sensitivity analysis with the goal to enhance the managerial insights rather than running technical tests with the model which are outside of this article and journal scope.

5.1. Impact of disruption duration

The first series of sensitivity experiments has examined the impact of disruption duration on network and performance indicators. We run 6 sensitivity experiments for disruption durations of 60 and 90 days and three sourcing strategies aligned with Section 4. The results are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3
Performance and network indicators in disruption scenarios with 60 days duration.

	Network indicators				Performance indicators						
	deg _{in}	deg _{in} ^(o)	deg _{out}	deg _{out} ^(o)	OTD	OTD ^(o)	FR	FR ^(o)	FSR	TTR (OTD _d)	TTR (FR _d)
a	6	0.40	6	0.40	0.93	0.07	0.93	0.07	0.60	60	60
b	11	0.39	11	0.39	0.97	0.03	0.97	0.03	0.60	60	60
c	18	0.40	18	0.40	1.00	0	1.00	0	0.60	0	0

It can be observed in Tables 3 and 4 that network static indicators do not change with the changes in disruption duration. This is explained by the consideration of structural changes only without production-ordering dynamics consideration. The performance indicators are sensitive to changes in disruption duration which is depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 summarizes data from Tables 2–4. It can be observed that network indicators do not show any time-sensitivity while the performance indicators are time-sensitive.

5.2. Impact of lead time and demand parameters

The second series of sensitivity experiments was conducted to prove the robustness of our results and associated managerial insights (cf. Sect. 6) with regards to two assumptions of simulation modelling, i.e., lead time of 3 days and equally distributed demand at all warehouses. In total, we run 12 sensitivity analyses subject to two different lead times (i.e., 5 and 7 days) and two different demand settings, i.e., 20 % of total demand at the nodes 7 and 8 and 60 % of the total demand at the nodes 7 and 8 (note that the baseline disruption scenario assumed 40 % of the total demand at the nodes 7 and 8).

With regard to lead time, as expected, the overall values of network and performance indicators have not shown any sensitivity since the lead time is shorter than the disruption time. However, the dynamics of performance indicators has changed compared to the baseline disruption scenario with a 3-days lead time. In particular, the OTD indicator changes have been postponed by 2 and 4 days for scenarios with 5 and 7 days of lead time, respectively. Changes in demand structure have translated in proportional changes in OTD, FR, and TTR indicators while the network indicators – as expected – have not been impacted. As these results are linear and proportional, we omit their graphical presentation since they do not lead to additional insights and are intuitive.

6. Managerial insights and practical implementation

In this section, we summarize the major insights and managerial recommendations based on the proposed concept and numerical analysis. Our main objective was to deepen the understanding of the interplay between network and performance indicators in analyzing the sourcing-related part of SC resilience, both as a system property (quality) and an outcome (quantity). We asked three essential questions, and now we summarize the main findings.

RQ1: How can network and performance indicators mutually enhance each other to measure SC resilience as both a property and an outcome?

Schoenherr et al. (2023) stress the importance of measuring in building SC resilience. SC resilience analysis includes four major steps, i.

Table 4
Performance and network indicators in disruption scenarios with 90 days duration.

	Network indicators				Performance indicators						
	deg _{in}	deg _{in} ^(o)	deg _{out}	deg _{out} ^(o)	OTD	OTD ^(o)	FR	FR ^(o)	FSR	TTR (OTD _d)	TTR (FR _d)
a	6	0.40	6	0.40	0.90	0.01	0.90	0.10	0.60	90	90
b	11	0.39	11	0.39	0.96	0.04	0.96	0.04	0.60	90	90
c	18	0.40	18	0.40	1.0	0	1.00	0	0.60	0	0

e., network mapping, shock scenarios, model (e.g., simulation), and performance assessment. The advantages of network theory applications to SC resilience are rigor methodology and well-developed apparatus for exploring cascading (ripple) effects in networks. Disadvantages of applying network theory include the limited complexity of networks that can be analyzed (especially in multi-echelon structures), the focus on structural aspects only (excluding material flows), and a static view of the supply chain, which may overlook dynamic changes. A crucial shortcoming is the focus on the network only without performance assessment. Schoenherr et al. (2023) and Burkhart and Bode (2024) underline the importance of translating performance measurement into action. To become a useful tool for resilience, network theory-based methods should include structure and process-product dynamics being integrated with material flows. Simulation methods allow for both dynamic modelling and performance assessment. Moreover, simulation and network science in combination with qualitative methods (e.g., panels and social simulation) can add value to resilience analysis, quantifying and validating qualitative assessments and opinions of experts (e.g., in designing shock scenarios).

RQ2. When and how can network and performance indicators inform about disruptions and recovery considering time delays?

Falcone et al. (2022) and Guntuka et al. (2024) highlight the importance of SC plasticity as a firm's capability to rapidly and significantly alter its network structure to accommodate substantial shifts and disruptions in the business environment. One essential contribution of our study lies in demonstrating how an integrated use of network science and discrete-event simulation enables a mixed-method approach that combines static and dynamic perspectives on SC resilience and structural reconfiguration. By utilizing node degrees as network indicators and measuring OTD, fulfillment rate, and time-to-recovery as performance indicators, we assessed how these metrics respond to disruptions under three different levels of sourcing flexibility. The key finding is that the closer the location of the measurement point to the disruption point, the shorter the delay in informing about resilience losses. For example, the fill rate indicator informs about disruption immediately because it is measured at warehouses. OTD is measured at customers, and informs about disruptions with time delays. Network indicators do not implicitly consider time because of their static nature.

RQ3. What managerial insights can be obtained from a combined network and performance indicators analysis?

Insight 1. OTD and FR indicate performance effect of a disruption on the customer side, considering recovery capabilities. FSR is in line with network indicators (especially node degrees) and so indicates the existence of structural disruptions in the network even if the customer performance is not disrupted.

Managerial recommendation 1. The resilience-measurement system should contain indicators that allow for the detection of disruptions through reduced network connectivity and adaptability (i.e., resilience as a quality) and observation of their effect (i.e., resilience as a quantity). A combination of network science and simulation allow for quantitative analysis of SC resilience performance considering both structural and process perspectives. Such an analysis can be helpful in multiple ways. On the one hand, managers can estimate the time available for recovery

before their customer would be affected by product shortages. It might allow for selection of appropriate recovery policies and resolving the trade-off between recovery time and costs. On the other hand, knowledge about disruptions at both customer and manufacturer sides might be helpful for finding collaborative recovery strategies fitting objectives of both parties. Managers can use our approach when implementing the Viable Supply Chain Model (Ivanov 2022b) and SC plasticity framework (Falcone et al., 2022; Guntuka et al., 2024) by using the proposed combination of network and performance indicators for structural network dynamics control.

Insight 2. FR gives a more realistic picture about inventory and warehouse-operations disruptions, while OTD displays the ripple-effect exposure of the supply chain (i.e., disruption propagation to the customer).

Managerial recommendation 2. Different indicators of resilience show disruptions and their effects at different times. In particular, a disruption can propagate downstream the supply chain. Its effect on the customer, however, will become visible with some delay. This calls for development of control towers that are capable to represent resilience performance at different SC echelons uncovering latent, time-delayed effects in a proactive way (MacCarthy and Ivanov 2022; Li et al., 2024b). The resulting knowledge about disruption propagation scale and scope can be of the utmost value for managers to identify affected nodes and links in the network and – most importantly – to predict the dynamics of disruption propagation.

Insight 3: Inverse analysis of in- and out-degrees for disruption scenarios where performance is achieved (i.e., the supply chain is resilient) can be considered for improving SC efficiency (i.e., lean resilience).

Managerial recommendation 3. If we can operate at 100 % performance without disrupted nodes or a disrupted arc, then we do not need them, and a detailed node in- and out-degree analysis can help detect such 'waste' elements in the network. Such an analysis can shed light on inefficient redundancies and so contribute to the development of the lean resilience as called for in Ivanov (2022a). While redundancies such as extra inventory, backup sourcing, and capacity reservations can help protect the supply chains and ensure operations continuity during disruptions, they might adversely affect efficiency. In these settings, two important questions arise: (i) do lean and resilience contradict each other? and (ii) can lean and resilience complement each other? The proposed analysis approach and simulation model can support managers in answering these questions.

Insight 4. FR, FSR, and network indicators react immediately to disruptions. OTD indicates both a disruption begin and its end with a delay. OTD is helpful for overall effect analysis from the customer point of view and the ripple effect, but it is less helpful in operative recognition of disruptions and how they end.

Managerial recommendation 4: Performance indicators inform us of the impact of a disruption, while network indicators show the presence of a disruption and the remaining adaptability of the network. It can be instructive to develop a resilience assessment system that contains indicators for both detection and impact of disruptions. In this way, managers can receive support for making informed decisions about recovery policies and fairly estimate the time available for deployment of recovery policies to avoid disruption impact at customers. This recommendation is in line with the findings of Burkhart and Bode (2024) connecting disruption intensity with disruption duration, and extending them by adding the time of deploying recovery actions (i.e.,

Time-to-Adapt (Mosayebi et al., 2024).

Insight 5. The longer the lead time, the later will the OTD inform about disruptions and recovery.

Managerial recommendation 5: It can be instructive to split the resilience analysis into product groups, which exhibit similar lead time characteristics. As such, it can be recommended to differentiate recovery policies for different products prioritizing the ones with shorter lead times and a faster performance impact at customers. This recommendation and insight echo the results obtained in Ivanov et al. (2023), which note that “resilience of product supply chains depends on the firm and network resilience, and higher firm and network resilience do not always automatically translate into higher resilience at the product level.”

Insight 6. The higher demand served by the disrupted nodes, the higher the impact on the performance but the network characteristics remain unchanged.

Managerial recommendation 6: Performance indicators can capture the dynamic changes in operational parameters and should be included in resilience analysis. In particular, it is instructive to develop a system of indicators for a monitoring of SC resilience performance. In addition, a proactive simulation of some demand or capacity increase/decrease scenarios can provide useful insights on preparing contingency plans, which can be deployed in a timely manner in an emergency case. This recommendation and insight shows the importance of simultaneous analysis of product and network levels in SC resilience. While the network characteristics provide information about structural consistency, product level characteristics take a more granular view taking into account demand, capacity, and inventory dynamics.

Insight 7. Network indicators are not sensitive to changes in operational parameters (e.g., demand, lead time, and disruption duration), while the performance indicators are time-sensitive.

Managerial recommendation 7. A combined application of network and performance indicators can inform decision-makers about both the detection of disruptions and their effects. Resilience assessment models can be mutually enhanced by including network characteristics and process dynamics. Integration of network and performance indicators allows for a mutual enhancement of structural and material flows model, which in their integrity can provide a comprehensive dashboard tool for building a control tower in SCs.

Insight 8. TTR indicator is sensitive to disruption duration and correlated to changes in OTD and FR.

Managerial recommendation 8. Analysis of SC recovery can be performed using TTR considering its dependence on the selection of OTD vs FR for computation. One important contribution of integrating network and performance indicators is the possibility to predict SC recovery/survival dynamics and identify critical nodes/suppliers without an explicit information from suppliers about their times-to-survive which extends the existing methods for TTR computations (Simchi-Levi et al., 2015).

With regards to the practical realisation of supply chain resilience management using the proposed combination of network and performance indicators, we discussed our approach with two supply chain directors. They supported our arguments and added that digital technology plays a critical role in the practical implementation of SC resilience analysis. We now generalise four major steps for the visibility and simulation of SC resilience that should be implemented for decision-making support using network and performance indicators.

Step 1: SC visibility and mapping. The first step is to create a digital SC model: i.e., to map network locations and flows with associated parameters, such as inventory, capacity, and demand (MacCarthy et al., 2022).

Step 2: Disruption visibility and mapping. The second step is to detect and predict disruptions both proactively and reactively. Data from external systems can be used here, as described in Kosasih and Brinrup (2022) and MacCarthy and Ivanov (2022).

Step 3: Monitoring, disruption simulation, and computation of indicators. In this step, SC and risk data are monitored. In the case of a disruption, SC and risk digital models are mapped with each other. This generates scenarios for SC stress-testing (in the proactive mode) and recovery simulation (in the reactive mode). Simulation of each scenario allows for the observation of network and performance indications, which quantify and visualise the disruption’s effect on the network’s structural connectivity and output performance.

Step 4: Decision-making and learning. In this step, decisions about recovery are made, supported by network and performance indicators. Moreover, it is important to document the knowledge obtained for the future (Jin et al., 2024).

Steps 1–4 are implemented as digital SC twins, which allows for stress-testing resilience and can be enhanced by the results of this study regarding decision-making support with network and performance indicators.

7. Conclusion

SC resilience can be viewed from perspectives of both network connectivity and performance persistence. Both views are important and complementary. While network and performance indicators of SC resilience have been studied separately, we are not aware of any published research combining these two perspectives in resilience assessment. Our study is the first to examine how network and performance indicators can mutually enhance each other in analysis of SC resilience as both a system property (quality) and an outcome (quantity).

We selected node degrees as a network indicator and OTD, FR, FSR, and TTR as performance indicators and, using the reactions of these indicators to a disruption, sourced strategies with three different degrees of flexibility (i.e., single sourcing, multiple sourcing, and full flexibility). The analysis, performed with the help of a discrete-event simulation in anyLogistix software, allowed us to deduce several useful managerial insights into what information each of the indicators can provide about network resilience, and what they cannot.

OTD and FR are particularly useful indicators to assess the performance effect of a disruption on the customer side in order to analyse resilience as a quantity. OTD reacts to disruptions with some delays, however, considering the distance between the disruption point and the customers, and is less suitable for the immediate detection of a disruption. Node degree and FSR are particularly suitable for the detection of structural disruptions in the network, even if customer performance is not disrupted. FR gives a more realistic picture about inventory or warehouse-operations disruptions, while OTD displays the ripple-effect exposure of the SC (i.e., disruption propagation to the customer). SC recovery analysis can be performed using TTR considering its dependence on the selection of OTD vs FR thresholds for computation. Sensitivity of the TTR indicator to disruption duration is a useful property allowing for comparing resilience of different sourcing strategies.

We conclude that a combined application of network and performance indicators can inform decision-makers about both the detection of disruptions and their effects. Resilience-assessment models can be mutually enhanced by including network characteristics and process dynamics. A combination of network and performance indicators is, therefore, important when considering both the structural and flow productivity aspects of SC resilience measurement.

As with any paper, ours has limitations. Our results hold true in the framework of the modelling assumptions. Relaxing some of these assumptions and including some additional parameters (e.g., bill-of-materials, different constellations of the lead time, recovery time and disruption periods, consideration of inventory-in-transit, available options for capacity expansions, time and space constraints on cross-regional re-routing possibilities in the case of disruptions, and the effect of different FR and OTD thresholds on TTR) may provide additional insights. Additional network and performance indicators could also be

used. Thus far, the generalised findings and insights from our study might need to be aligned with concrete business environments in future research. As another future research direction, resilience measurement in the setting of long-term SC crises (such as a pandemic) could be named, e.g., using theory of SC viability (Ivanov, 2024; Ruel et al., 2024; Ivanov et al., 2023).

Declarations

The author(s) declare no conflict of interest (financial or non-financial).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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